

ELIXIR Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens 2024-2026

Work Package 1 - ELIXIR Strategy for Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens

D1.2 Report and Roadmap on Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens in ELIXIR 2025-2026

Tier: Science Tier

Priority Area: BFSP

Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on the implementation of ELIXIR's Biodiversity, Food Security, and Pathogens (BFSP) Priority Area strategy during 2025–2026, advancing the ELIXIR 2024–28 Programme's Science Tier objectives. Building on the strategy document published as D1.1, the focus has shifted from planning to concrete action.

Two open calls were conducted, resulting in the selection of nine projects. These projects are delivering tangible FAIR data services and tools for their respective communities, and have demonstrated value as coordination drivers despite operating under limited budgets. The selection process was transparent and rigorous, underpinned by an independent review committee.

The D1.1 strategy remains fit for purpose through 2026 and requires no revision. However, limited cross-community coordination has emerged from the current project portfolio, informing a key improvement for the 2027–2028 work programme: a more integrated, coordinated implementation framework.

Stakeholder engagement is strong, with broad member interest in shaping the next programme cycle. The strategy and selected projects are publicly accessible via Zenodo and the ELIXIR BFSP webpage, ensuring transparency and visibility across the life science community.

Document info

Responsible Participant	FR-INRAE
Dissemination level	PU

Author List

Node	Institution	Name, surname	ORCID
FR-Fra... ▾	INRA	Cyril Pommier	0000-0002-9040-8733

Reviewers: Tereza Manousaki, Robert Waterhouse

Abbreviations and Acronyms

BFSP	Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens
LLM	Large Language Model

Contents

Executive Summary	1
Document info	2
Author List	2
Abbreviations and Acronyms	2
Contents	2
Deliverable description	3
Outcomes and expected impact	4
Dissemination Plans	4

Deliverable description

The BFSP Priority Area activity over 2025-2026 has mainly focused on the implementation of the BFSP Strategy delivered in D1.1 through concrete actions. During these two years, this has been mainly achieved through two open calls that supported mobilisation and drove actions focused on BFSP-related needs. The Version 1.0 of the strategy document describes ELIXIR's Strategy for developing the Biodiversity, Food Security, and Pathogens (BFSP) Priority Area within the Science Tier of the ELIXIR 2024-28 Programme. It was developed by the BFSP Priority Area co-leads, with support from the ELIXIR Hub, and with input and feedback from ELIXIR members across Nodes, Communities, Focus Groups, and Platforms. So far, it has proven useful and does not require updates either for the current work programme or for the upcoming 2027-2028. Therefore no new version is planned.

Two open calls (M1.1 and M1.2) have resulted in the selection of nine projects. These projects are currently implementing concrete services for ELIXIR Members and demonstrate their importance as coordination drivers within communities. A fair selection process was set up with independent reviewers and the formation of a selection committee chaired by the ELIXIR director. It is noteworthy that while the selection process was rather straightforward for the first call, it was much more challenging during the second call as it attracted many more submissions. While each project advances specific BFSP-related actions, the activities so far have promoted little intercommunity interactions or enhanced coordination. Therefore, the upcoming 2027-2028 work programme will set up a more coordinated implementation of the BFSP strategy that aims to address this goal.

Nine selected projects

- BioDiv-FAIR-Checker: Raising FAIRness of European biodiversity data through ELIXIR-aligned standards, services and training
- Building FAIR metadata standards for non-human pathogen genomic and phenotypic data
- Creation of a virtual assistant guiding plant researchers in making their datasets FAIR compliant
- FAIRferm: FAIRifying microbiome-metabolome time-series data from food fermentation processes
- E-PAN: Enhancing pan-genome analysis in plants
- FAIRyMAGs: Optimising Metagenomics Assembled Genomes building: workflow finalisation, training material development, real data evaluation and resource allocation tool creation

- HARVEST: Handling and alignment of plant research FAIRification – value through the use of ELIXIR data Standards and Tools
- KYBELE: Knowledge Yield from Biodiversity Literature through Large Language Model (LLM) Extraction
- Odyssey: Connecting molecular and geographical biodiversity data

Outcomes and expected impact

The work supporting Deliverable D1.2 is a follow up of D1.1 that built the Strategy designed to guide ELIXIR's priorities and decision making when participating in activities in support of Biodiversity, Food Security, and Pathogens Research. It clearly reflects the diverse activities and ambitions of ELIXIR Members in the BFSP domain thanks to its collaborative building process. The multi-annual Roadmap for investments in the 2025-2026 period concretely delivered the four projects selected from the second Open Call. The selected projects, despite their limited budget, have demonstrated their impact as coordination drivers for BFSP-related ELIXIR Communities.

Work coordinated by the co-leads has also advanced consultations to develop a renewed Work Plan for 2027-2028 and will subsequently solicit and integrate input from engaged Members into the 2029+ Programme. Thanks to the interest of Members from all communities regarding the building of the 2027-2028 Work Plan, a bottom-up development has produced a larger-than-expected set of proposed activities. The organisation of the programme into Work Packages that mirror the strategy structure is well accepted and forms a strong and consensual foundation for the activities of the next two years.

Dissemination Plans

The D1.1 Strategy (version 1) has been made publicly available as a publication on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/15133254>.

The nine selected projects are described on the BFSP webpage <https://elixir-europe.org/how-we-work/scientific-programme/science/bfsp>.